

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF UN-NOTCHED AND NOTCHED 3D BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The static and dynamic mechanical properties of notched and un-notched 3D braided composites were studied. The effect of longitudinal laid-in yarn was investigated comparing to low braiding angle composites. The longitudinal stiffness of the specimen was monitored during the fatigue loading and residual strength of the samples surviving millions cycles was tested. The open-hole static and fatigue properties of 3D braided composite and laminate composite were compared. It was found that the static and fatigue properties of low angle 3D braided behave similarly to longitudinally reinforced 3D braided composites. The static result confirms that the 3D braided composites are less notch sensitive than laminated composites. Preliminary results show that notched 3D braided composites can also retain higher fatigue strength under tension-tension fatigue loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over half a century since the rediscovery of three dimensional (3D) braiding technology, 3D braided composites continue to attract the interest of researchers in academia and industry across a wide variety of matrix types including carbon (CCC), ceramic (CMC), metal (MMC) and polymer (PMC) matrix composites [1]. The sustained interest in 3D braided composites can be attributed to the proven damage tolerance, delamination-free characteristics, and the ability of creating net complex shape structures in a digitally controlled manner. Macander [3] demonstrated that 3D braided composites have greater capacity for damage tolerance than laminates, also they found the 3D braided composites are sensitive to the cutting edge, which will ruin the integrity of the 3D braided composites. Ko [4] presented FGM (Fabric Geometry Model) to predict strength and modulus prediction of 3D braided composite. Gause and Alper [2] evaluated a wide range of the static and dynamic mechanical properties of 3D braided composites, including open hole static strength and tensile fatigue behavior. For the first time, they demonstrated that the 3D braided composites are notch (open-hole) insensitive. In the subsequent years a few studies have been published on the fatigue behavior of braided composites [5-7], but none included open-hole fatigue behavior. In last decade, a few researchers used the numerical method to analyze the static and dynamic properties of 3D braided composite to avoid the time consuming and highly cost experiments [8-12].

The fatigue failure of notched composites is an important aeronautical structural engineering concern and Damage Tolerant Design Principles[13]. Considering that 3D braided composites possess excellent open-hole strength retention, the authors also stressed the need for information on the fatigue behavior of open-hole 3D braided composites.

Accordingly it is the objective of this study to examine the open-hole effects on the tension-tension fatigue behavior of 3D braided composite.

2 EXPERIMENTAL MATERIAL FABRICATION

3D braided preforms were produced using AS4 6K carbon yarns on a Cartesian four-step 3D braider. Two styles of the braided composites were fabricated and tested. Style I was the basic (1 × 1) pattern. Style II incorporated 40% longitudinal lay-in yarns. The 3D braids have a surface braiding angle of $\pm 12^\circ$. The preforms were wetted thoroughly by epoxy system consisting West System 105 and 209 hardeners (mix ratio = 3.68:1 by weight) and molded using a closed mold for at least 24 hours to cure under constant pressure at room temperature. The fully cured composite was released from the mold, to avoid the cutting edges effect [3]. For un-notched and notched samples, the estimated fiber volume fraction was 59% for Style I and 62% for Style II.

Properties	Matrix	AS4-6k
Tensile modulus, GPa	2.74	231
Tensile strength, MPa	51	4447
Strain, %	3.6%	1.7
Density, g/m ³	1.16	1.78

Table 1: Properties of Matrix and carbon

The geometry and dimension of the composite specimen with a hole is shown in Figure 1, target width and thickness for all specimens (notched and unnotched) were 25 mm and 3 mm, respectively. The hole (5mm) was drilled at the center of the specimen using special CBN diamond core drill bits. The width-to-diameter ratio of the hole size is 5.

Figure1.Geometry and dimensions of un-notched specimen

3 QUASI-STATIC AND FATIGUE TEST METHODS

The static un-notched tensile strength and notched were conducted according to the ASTM D3039 and ASTM D 5766, respectively. For static tests, 5 samples were tested on an Instron tensile tester to obtain the mean tensile strength, with cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. The un-notched and notched compression strength was also examined, followed ASTM D3410 and ASTM D6484, respectively, with a testing speed of 1.5 mm/min.

For tension-tension (R=0.1, 3Hz) fatigue study, the specimens were tested according to ASTM D3479 standard, 10 samples were tested to obtain the S-N curve for each group. All tests were performed in a MTS closed-loop servo-hydraulic test machine equipped with self-aligning hydraulic grips. Cycle rate of 3Hz was chosen to minimize the effects of specimen heating. Specimens surviving 10^6 cycles were residual strength tested.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cross-section of 3-D braided composite is shown in Figure 2. The yarn cross section of pure braids is usually more uniform than Style I with axial yarns.

Figure 2. Photographs of cross-sectional areas of 3-D braided composite: (a) Style I; (b) Style II

Static results

Table 2 summarized the tension, compression, and OHT (open-hole tension) and OHC (open-hole compression) strength of the 3D braided composites and their comparison with the published results on 3D braided composites and lamination composites. Comparing style I and style II structure, no matter under tension and/or compression loading, notched and/or un-notched, the value deviation is not significant. The braids with 42% axial yarn did not show higher strength in comparison to basic pattern, which means the involved axial yarns did not improve the structural properties under $\pm 12^\circ$ braiding angle.

Compared with laminated composites, all the 3D braided composites keep higher level of OHT strength retention. For instance, the un-notched 18-ply ($0 \pm 20^\circ$) laminates [14], the similar tensile strength with the present results, after drilling the hole, can only keep 58% of the tensile strength. For 0° Hexcel ply laminates [15], the un-notched tensile strength is 2205 MPa, while after drilling the hole, the strength decline to 438 MPa dramatically, which is only half of the open-hole 3D braided composites. Our data showed that both 3D braided composites can keep 74%-80% of the tensile strength, thus, the final notched tensile strength of 3D braided is much higher than that of laminated composites.

Normally 3D braided composites can also retain higher OHC strength, except the 24-ply [2] case, while it's original compression strength is pretty low. Even the un-notched compression strength is lower than laminates, while the notched compression strength is similar to notched laminates. From the observation of the failure mode under compression loading, there is no buckling noticed in 3D braids case, mainly because of the nature of integrated structure of 3D braided composite, which will benefit the damage resistance. On the other hand, for laminates, the natural delamination in compression inducing buckling will render the structure fail earlier.

In comparison with laminates, our results confirms Gause's finding [2] that the 3D braided composites are less notch sensitive than laminated composites. Thus, considering the advantages of 3D braids, it will be an attractive candidate for structural application.

Table 3: Strength of 3D braided and laminated composites

	Tension				Compression			
	V_f	Without Hole/MPa	With Hole/MPa	Strength Retention %	Without Hole/MPa	With Hole/MPa	Strength Retention %	
3-D BRAIDED	Style I($0^\circ \pm 12^\circ$)	59	1173 \pm 61	910 \pm 57	80	589 \pm 53	368 \pm 61	62
	Style II($\pm 12^\circ$)	62	1279 \pm 80	951 \pm 45	74	596 \pm 56	406 \pm 33	68
	C12K/3501($0^\circ \pm 20^\circ$)[2]	60	668	661	99	429	314	73
	150G PEEK/AS4($0^\circ \pm 20^\circ$)[14]	60	586	463	79	-	259	-
LAMINATES	Hexcel Ply 8552[15]	60	2205	432	20	-	-	-
	18-ply APC-2[($0^\circ \pm 20^\circ$) ₄ ,0] _s [14]	60	1081	628	58	646	363	56
	24-ply AS43501[-45/0/+45/90] _s [2]	60	911	445	49	420	403	96
	16-ply($0^\circ \pm 20^\circ$)[16]	63	703	472	67	665	398	60

Tension–tension fatigue results

The stress-life curve of two types of notched 3D braided composites is shown in Figure 3(a). Using same ratio, Style II composites tend to show better fatigue life compared to style I. Figure 3 (b) shows a comparison of the normalized T-T fatigue strength of notched 3D braided composites with notched lamination composites[6] [17]. It was noted that both two types of notched braids under tension-tension fatigue loading can retain higher proportion of notched static strength.

Figure 3. Tension-tension fatigue results: (a) Life to failure; (b) S-N curve, R=0.1

Figure 4 shows the in situ elastic modulus normalized by the initial modulus versus the corresponding cycle count normalized by the numbers of cycles to failure. The longitudinal stiffness of the composite is calculated using the load-displacement curve. Figure 4 (a) shows that the stiffness of the material reduces significantly after the first few hundred cycles. Later, there is only slight change in stiffness until the end of the fatigue test. The cycle curves of specimen at maximum 750MPa fatigue loading is shown in Figure 4 (b), the slope of the cycle curves only slightly decreases. The decrease of the cycle slope suggests that there is indeed some gradual stiffness reduction of the material, caused by the damage accumulation during cycling, but usually it has no more than 10% stiffness reduction.

Figure 4. Stiffness evolution during the life: (a) evolution of the style II specimen in-plane stiffness; (b) Some stress vs. displacement curves at maximum stress 750 MPa

Residual strength analysis

In order to measure the residual strength of the specimen after fatigue, the post-fatigue quasi-static tests were performed on the specimen surviving 10^6 cycles at 700 MPa stress level at 3Hz. Figure 5 compares the stress –strain behavior of the original sample and the coupon after fatigue loading. From the residual strength tests, it is evident that fatigue loading does not show much influence on the coupon’s modulus nor the strength.

Figure 5: Comparison of the Stress-Strain curve between the virgin composite specimens and fatigue tested specimens.

Failure mechanism

Photographs of failed fatigue specimens are presented in Figures 6-9. As shown in Figure 6, the two types of un-notched 3D braided coupons perform different failure behavior. Under tension, the pure braids tend to show clear crack, while this is not true for the 42% axial yarn braids. For notched specimens, the cracks initiate traversing the hole and travel along the braiding angle for a certain distance, then propagate transversely, finally render the specimen fail, while clear crack still show up on pure braided coupons, not for with axial yarn, as shown in Figure 7.

Under tension-tension fatigue loading, both types show similar failure mechanism, as shown in Figure 8. Early in life, cracks showed up on the surface of the specimens around the hole and along the braiding yarn, which mainly because of the rich resin area break first, but did not grow across the coupons. Thereafter, there was almost no change during the whole cycles until the specimens catastrophically break. There were mainly two types of failure behavior macroscopically, one was fiber break transversely along the hole, and the other one was crack traversed the hole along the braiding angle.

The open-hole fatigue failure mechanism of 3D braided composite was totally different compared to the static case, as shown in Figure 8. For Style I, crack tended to follow the longitudinal yarns and the specimen usually fail with large damaged area, however, style II structure could stop crack propagation significantly and contained less damaged area. Under fatigue loading, damages accumulated in the coupon, inducing matrix crack and fiber decreases strength, finally caused the specimen suddenly to break at the threshold value. Comparing two types of braided composites, the style II showed transverse breaks with small damaged area, while, style I showed explosively failure surface. Fracture surface of notched specimens after the fatigue tests are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 6: Photographs of un-notched specimens after the tensile tests: (a) Style I; (b) Style II

Figure 7: Photographs of notched specimens after the quasi-static tensile tests: (a) Style I; (b) Style II

Figure 8: Photographs of notched specimens after the fatigue tests: (a) Style I; (b) Style II

Figure 9: Fracture surface of notched specimens after the fatigue tests: (a) Style I; (b) Style II

5 CONCLUSIONS

The static and dynamic properties of two types of notched and un-notched 3D braided composites were studied, and compared with laminated composites. The two types of 3D braided composites behaved similarly in static properties. The static result confirmed that the 3D braided composites are indeed less notch sensitive than laminated composites. Preliminary results showed that pure notched braided composites have better fatigue resistance than braided composite with axial yarn. Both notched 3D braided composites can retain higher fatigue strength than laminates under tension-tension fatigue loading. The two types of braided composites behaved differently in failure mechanism under static tension loading. The style II composites showed clear crack at failure, while this is not true for style I. Under tension-tension fatigue loading, the notched 3D braided composites show 'toothbrush' fracture surface, which is different from static case, style I tends to fail following the longitudinal yarns with large failure area and explosively failure surface, style II usually transversely break with small damaged area and contain damage better.

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REFERENCES

1. Ko, F.K. *Three-dimensional fabrics for composites*. Elsevier Science Publishers, Textile Structural Composites, 1989: p. 129-171.
2. Gause, L.W. and J.M. Alper, *Structural properties of braided graphite/epoxy composites*. Journal of Composites, Technology and Research, 1987. 9(4): p. 141-150.
3. Macander, A.B., R.M. Crane, and E.T. Camponeschi. *Fabrication and mechanical properties of multidimensionally (XD) braided composite materials*. in *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Seventh Conference)*. 1986. ASTM International.
4. Ko, F.K. *Tensile strength and modulus of a three-dimensional braid composite*. in *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Seventh Conference)*. 1986. ASTM International.
5. Carvelli, V., et al., *Quasi-static and fatigue tensile behavior of a 3D rotary braided carbon/epoxy composite*. Journal of Composite Materials, 2012. 47(25): p. 3195-3209.
6. Portanova, M.A., *Fatigue resistance of unnotched and post impact (+/-30 deg/0 deg) 3-D braided composites*. 1994.
7. Portanova, M.A. and J.W. Deaton, *Impact and Fatigue Resistance of a [$\pm 30^\circ/0^\circ$] 3-D Braided Carbon Epoxy Composite*, in *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture: Fifth Volume*. 1995, ASTM International.
8. Schreiber, F., et al. *Novel three-dimensional braiding approach and its products*. in *17th International Conference on Composite Materials, Edinburgh, UK*. 2009.
9. Sun, B., R. Liu, and B. Gu, *Numerical simulation of three-point bending fatigue of four-step 3-D braided rectangular composite under different stress levels from unit-cell approach*. Computational Materials Science, 2012. 65: p. 239-246.
10. Xu, K., *A numerical study on the progressive failure of 3D four-directional braided composites*. Advances in Materials Science and Engineering, 2013.

11. Jacques, S., I. De Baere, and W. Van Paepegem, *Application of periodic boundary conditions on multiple part finite element meshes for the meso-scale homogenization of textile fabric composites*. Composites Science and Technology, 2014. 92: p. 41-54.
12. Zhang, C., J. Curiel-Sosa, and T.Q. Bui, *A novel interface constitutive model for prediction of stiffness and strength in 3D braided composites*. Composite Structures, 2017. 163: p. 32-43.
13. Dalgarno, R.W., et al., *Failure simulations of open-hole IM7/977-3 coupons subjected to fatigue loading using Autodesk Heliuss PFA*. Journal of Composite Materials, 2017. 51(15): p. 2119-2129.
14. Hua, C.T., J.-N. Chu, and F.K. Ko, *Damage tolerance of three-dimensional commingled PEEK/carbon composites*, in *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Tenth Volume)*. 1992, ASTM International.
15. https://www.hexcel.com/user_area/content_media/raw/AS4_HexTow_DataSheet.pdf.
16. Wang, J., P. Callus, and M. Bannister, *Experimental and numerical investigation of the tension and compression strength of un-notched and notched quasi-isotropic laminates*. composite Structures, 2004. 64(3-4): p. 297-306.
17. Nixon-Pearson, O., et al., *Damage development in open-hole composite specimens in fatigue. Part 1: Experimental investigation*. Composite Structures, 2013. 106: p. 882-889.